

CHILD RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D3.2 - ChildRescue Platform and Mobile App, Early Prototype

Workpackage: WP3 – ChildRescue Platform Architecture Definition and Implementation

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ChildRescue Project Profile

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Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	European Federation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children AISBL - Missing Children Europe (MCE)	Belgium
	The Smile of the Child (SoC)	Greece
	Foundation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children – (Child Focus)	Belgium
	Hellenic Red Cross (REDCROSS)	Greece
	Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences (FRA-UAS)	Germany
	SINGULARLOGIC ANONYMI ETAIREIA PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON KAI EFARMOGON PLIROFORIKIS (SLG)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
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	SUITE5 DATA INTELLIGENCE SOLUTIONS LIMITED (S5)	Cyprus

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Executive Summary

The present document presents the results of the first iteration of “T3.2 - Platform Development and Deployment” and “T3.3 – Mobile App Design and Development” which consists of a low fidelity, functional mock-up version of the platform that will be delivered for early assessment by the end users. The functional mockups of the platform are implemented using Figma¹, a free online design collaborative platform. The platform functional mockups can be downloaded from: https://alfresco.epu.ntua.gr/share/s/O6TB_bY4QFu8Y7q3tZROYQ or accessed online from: <https://www.figma.com/file/UvYjRcAZsSAQ1R7hWa6GKzSx/ChildRescue>.

¹ <https://www.figma.com/>

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

The present document presents the results of the first iteration of “T3.2 - Platform Development and Deployment” and “T3.3 – Mobile App Design and Development” which consists of a low fidelity, functional mock-up version of the platform that will be delivered for early assessment by the end users. The functional mockups of the platform are implemented using Figma², a free online design collaborative platform. The platform functional mockups can be downloaded from: https://alfresco.epu.ntua.gr/share/s/O6TB_bY4QFu8Y7q3tZROYQ or accessed online from: <https://www.figma.com/file/UvYjRcAZsSAQ1R7hWa6GKzSx/ChildRescue>.

The mockups will guide the development of the first prototype of the ChildRescue Platform which will be delivered on M18.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows:

In Section 1, an introductory description of the document is provided, communicating its scope, its structure and the working methodology. In Section 2, the screenshots of the implemented functional mockups are presented, based on each user role. Section 3, concludes the document, while in the Annex I: Updated User stories the updated user stories are provided.

1.3 Working methodology

The definition of the functional mockups was implemented in three iterations. A first definition of the mobile application and the web platform were developed based on the results of WP1 and WP2 and more specifically, based on the user requirements as they are defined in “D1.1 - User Requirements” and the ChildRescue integrated methodology as it is described in “D1.3 - ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I”. The results of the first definition of the mockups were presented to the end users at the Second Plenary Meeting of ChildRescue in Frankfurt, 6-7 November, 2018 where the user stories were also updated. The consortium capitalised upon the feedback received from the demonstration of the first version of the mockups which was integrated in the elaboration of the specifications of the mobile app and the web platform in order to define the second version of the functional mockups. The second version of the functional mockups was presented to the end users in a targeted workshop on 13th December 2018 in UBITECH’s premises. The input of the workshop, as well as, additional feedback received from the pilots in bilateral Telcos after the workshop was collected in order to update and conclude to the final version of the mockups. The following table presents in detail the three iterations that were mentioned above.

Mockups Release version	Delivery date	Event	Sources	User roles
1.0	6/11/2018	Second Plenary Meeting in Frankfurt	D1.2, D1.3	Anonymous user, Registered user,

² <https://www.figma.com/>

				Volunteer, Case Manager, Hosting Facility Manager, Organisation Coordinator, Organisation Owner
2.0	13/12/2018	Functional Mockups Workshop at UBITECH, Greece	Second Plenary Meeting in Frankfurt, Updated user stories	Anonymous user, Registered user, Volunteer, Case Manager, Network Manager, Hosting Facility Manager, Organisation Coordinator, Organisation Owner, Platform Administrator
3.0 (Final)	21/12/2018	Bilateral discussions with pilots	Additional comments from pilots	Anonymous user, Registered user, Volunteer, Case Manager, Network Manager, Hosting Facility Manager, Organisation Coordinator, Organisation Owner, Platform Administrator

2 Functional Mockups

2.1 Anonymous user

2.1.1 Login & Register

Figure 2-1 Welcome screen 1

Figure 2-2 Welcome screen 2

SKIP →

ChildRescue

LOGIN

LOGIN

[Forgot your password?](#)

Don't have an account? [Sign up](#)

Figure 2-3 Login

SKIP →

ChildRescue

REGISTER

REGISTER

OR register with:

Already have an account? [Log in](#)

Figure 2-4 Register

Figure 2-5 Login (Web platform)

Figure 2-6 Register (Web platform)

2.1.2 Home/Dashboard

Figure 2-7 Home page: no alerts in the area of the user’s current location

Figure 2-8 Home page: two alerts in the area of the user’s current location

Figure 2-9 Home page (Web platform)

2.1.3 Main menu

Figure 2-10 Anonymous user – main menu

2.1.4 Alerts

Figure 2-11 Anonymous user – alerts in user’s area

Figure 2-12 Anonymous user – alerts in user’s area (Web platform)

2.1.5 View missing child case

Figure 2-13 Anonymous user – View missing child incident: the related case signifies that the two children were missing together

Figure 2-14 Anonymous user – View missing child incident: the related case signifies that the two children were missing together

2.1.6 Organisations

Figure 2-15 Anonymous user – Organisations

Figure 2-16 Anonymous user – Organisations – Organisation details

Figure 2-17 Anonymous user – Organisations (Web platform)

Figure 2-18 Anonymous user – Organisations – Organisation details (Web platform)

2.1.7 Provide information for specific case

Figure 2-19 Anonymous user – Provide information for specific case

Figure 2-20 Anonymous user – Provide information for specific case – Thank you message

Figure 2-21 Anonymous user – Provide information for specific case (Web platform)

2.1.8 Provide information

Figure 2-22 Anonymous user – Provide information (1/3)

Figure 2-23 Anonymous user – Provide information (2/3)

Figure 2-24 Anonymous user – Provide information (3/3)

Figure 2-25 Anonymous user – Provide information – Helpful information

2.2 Simple user

2.2.1 Dashboard

Figure 2-26 Dashboard: no alerts in the user's current area

Figure 2-27 Dashboard: no alerts in the user's current area

Figure 2-28 Simple user – Dashboard (Web platform)

2.2.2 Main menu

Figure 2-29 Simple user – main menu

2.2.3 Notifications

Figure 2-30 Simple user – Notifications

2.2.4 Alerts

Figure 2-31 Simple user – Alerts (list)

Figure 2-32 Simple user – Alerts (tiles)

Figure 2-33 Simple user – Alerts (Web platform)

2.2.5 View missing child case

Figure 2-34 Simple user – View missing child case

Figure 2-35 Simple user – Missing child case – Information provided by the user in the past

← **Provide information**

Yussef Osso, Athens, Greece

PROVIDE INFORMATION

 ADD MEDIA (Optional)

Child Location

Telephone (Optional)

Information about the missing child

SUBMIT INFORMATION

Figure 2-36 Simple user – Provide information

Figure 2-37 Simple user – View provided feedback

Figure 2-38 Simple user – View provided feedback

Figure 2-39 Simple user – View case (Web platform)

2.2.6 Closed cases

Figure 2-40 Simple user – View closed case

Figure 2-41 Simple user – View closed case (Web platform)

2.2.7 Organisations

Figure 2-42 Simple user – Organisations

Figure 2-43 Simple user – Organisation details

2.2.8 Profile

Figure 2-44 Simple user – View profile

Figure 2-45 Simple user – Edit profile

Figure 2-46 Simple user – View profile (Web platform)

Figure 2-47 Simple user – Volunteering

2.3 Volunteer

2.3.1 Dashboard

Figure 2-48 Volunteer – Dashboard: view alert on the map

Figure 2-49 Volunteer – Dashboard (Web platform)

2.3.2 Followed alerts

Figure 2-50 Volunteer – Followed alerts

2.3.3 Main menu

Figure 2-51 Volunteer – Main menu

2.3.4 Notifications

Figure 2-52 Volunteer – Notifications

2.3.5 View missing child case

Figure 2-53 Volunteer – View missing child case

Figure 2-54 Volunteer – View missing child case (Web profile)

2.3.6 Rescue team invitation notification

Figure 2-55 Volunteer – Rescue team invitation notification

2.3.7 Collaboration space

Figure 2-56 Volunteer – Collaboration Spaces

Figure 2-57 Volunteer – Collaboration Spaces – Timeline

Figure 2-58 Volunteer – Collaboration Space – Chatrooms

Figure 2-59 Volunteer – Collaboration Space – Chat

Figure 2-60 Volunteer – Collaboration Space – Members in map

Figure 2-61 Volunteer – Collaboration Space – Members list

PROVIDE FEEDBACK

Figure 2-62 Volunteer – Collaboration Space – Feedback provided by the volunteer

Figure 2-63 Volunteer – Collaboration Space –My tasks

2.3.8 Team leader

<p>Figure 2-64 Team leader – Collaboration Space – View feedback from all rescue team members</p>	<p>Figure 2-65 Team leader – Collaboration Space – Coordination chatroom with Network manager</p>

2.3.9 Profile

Figure 2-66 Volunteer – View profile

Figure 2-67 Volunteer – Edit profile

2.4 Hosting Facility Manager

2.4.1 Dashboard

Figure 2-68 Hosting Facility Manager – Dashboard

Figure 2-69 Hosting Facility Manager – Notifications

2.4.2 UM Management

Figure 2-70 Hosting Facility Manager – UM case

Figure 2-71 Hosting Facility Manager – UM case analytics

Figure 2-72 Hosting Facility Manager – Create UM profile

Figure 2-73 Hosting Facility Manager – Create UM profile – Demographics

Figure 2-74 Hosting Facility Manager – Send UM profile to another Hosting Facility Manager – Select Hosting Facility Manager

Figure 2-75 Hosting Facility Manager – Send UM profile to another Hosting Facility Manager – Select profile sections

2.4.3 Attendance book

Figure 2-76 Hosting Facility Manager – Attendance book (list)

Figure 2-77 Hosting Facility Manager – Attendance book (tiles)

2.5 Case Manager

2.5.1 Dashboard

Figure 2-78 Case manager – Dashboard

Figure 2-79 Case manager – Notifications

2.5.2 Case management

Figure 2-80 Case Manager – Case list (tiles)

Figure 2-81 Case Manager – Case details

Figure 2-82 Case Manager – Case management – Information

Figure 2-83 Case Manager – Case management – Validation request

Figure 2-84 Case Manager – Case management – Case Analysis

Figure 2-85 Case Manager – Case management – Timeline

Figure 2-86 Case Manager – Case management – Create amber alert

2.5.3 Collaboration spaces

Figure 2-87 Case Manager – Collaboration map: view alerts, evidence, resources on map

Figure 2-88 Case Manager – Collaboration spaces list

Figure 2-89 Case Manager – Collaboration spaces – Collaboration space for a specific missing child

2.5.4 Public alerts

Figure 2-90 Case Manager – Public alerts

2.6 Network Manager

2.6.1 Case coordination

Figure 2-91 Network Manager – Team management – Create rescue team

Figure 2-92 Network Manager – Team management – View rescue team

2.6.2 Collaboration spaces

Figure 2-93 Network Manager – Collaboration Spaces (list)

Figure 2-94 Network Manager – Collaboration Spaces (tiles)

Figure 2-95 Network Manager – Collaboration Spaces (tiles) (Mobile app)

Figure 2-96 Network Manager – Collaboration space of specific case

Figure 2-97 Network Manager – Collaboration space of specific case – Rescue team overview

Child Rescue Search for...

Home / Collaboration Space / Yossuf Osso / Rescue Team 1

Rescue Team 1
4 members

CHATROOMS
4 chatrooms created

Name	Members	Created At
Chatroom #1	2 members	21/10/2018
Chatroom #2	3 members	21/10/2018
Chatroom #3	4 members	21/10/2018
Chatroom #4	2 members	21/10/2018

FEEDBACK
15 new evidence

Feedback file	Received
feedback1.png	13/11/2018, 12:55 PM
feedback2.png	13/11/2018, 12:55 PM

ANNOUNCEMENTS

- 21/10/2018, 14:42 PM: ...tion space of the Child ilable to Team Leaders
- 21/10/2018, 14:42 PM: ...laboration space of the

TASKS
3 new tasks

Task: Check the location of Evidence

Case Timeline

TODAY

- 10:15 AM: Maria Papadopoulou joined the rescue team
- 09:30 AM: Kate Smith uploaded new feedback in the collaboration space. [See file](#)
- 09:15 AM: Kate Smith sent a new message on the chatroom #1

YESTERDAY

- 10:15 AM: Maria Papadopoulou joined the rescue team
- 09:30 AM: Kate Smith uploaded a new evidence in the collaboration space. [VIEW FILE](#)
- 09:15 AM: Kate Smith sent a new message on the chat

TODAY

- 10:15 AM: Maria Papadopoulou joined the rescue team
- 09:30 AM: Kate Smith uploaded new feedback in the collaboration space. [See file](#)
- 09:15 AM: Kate Smith sent a new message on the chatroom #1

Figure 2-98 Network Manager – Collaboration space of specific case – Rescue team overview – Timeline

Figure 2-99 Network Manager – Collaboration Space – Timeline

<p>Figure 2-100 Network Manager – Collaboration Space – Chat – Create chatroom</p>	<p>Figure 2-101 Network Manager – Collaboration Space – Chat</p>

Figure 2-102 Network Manager – Collaboration Space – Members – Add member

Figure 2-103 Network Manager – Collaboration Space – Members – View members on the map

Figure 2-104 Network Manager – Collaboration Space – Feedback

Figure 2-105 Network Manager – Collaboration Spaces – Create task

2.7 Organisation Coordinator

2.7.1 Case management

Figure 2-106 Organisation Coordinator – Case Management – Case list (tiles)

The screenshot shows the 'Child Rescue' application interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Analytics, Case management, Case coordination, Collaboration map, Public alerts, Archived cases, and Collaboration Spaces (Dominique Smith). The main content area shows a search bar, user profile (John Doe), and breadcrumb navigation (/ Case management / Yussuf Osso). The case title is 'Yussef Osso' with a status of 'MISSING CHILD'. Action buttons include 'SEND EVALUATION', 'CLOSE CASE', '+ AMBER ALERT', and '+ MISSING CHILD'. Below the title are tabs for 'Case', 'Feedback (3)', 'Case Analysis', 'Additional Information', and 'Case Timeline'. The 'Case' tab is active, displaying:

- INFORMATION:** Missing From: 03/07/2018, Date Of Birth: 19/07/2016. Includes social media links for Facebook and Instagram.
- ADMINISTRATORS:** Network Manager: Kate Pappa, Case Manager: Maria Papadopoulou.
- DETAILS:** Date Of Birth: 19/07/2006 (12 yo), Eye Color: Black, Hair Color: Brown.
- DESCRIPTION:** A paragraph of text in Greek describing the missing child's details and the search process.
- RELATED CASES:** A small profile picture of 'Fawad Rasuli'.

 An 'Edit case' button is visible in the top right of the case details area.

Figure 2-107 Organisation Coordinator – Case Management – Case details

This screenshot shows the same case management interface but with the case status changed to 'CLOSED'. The breadcrumb navigation remains the same. The case title is 'Yussef Osso' with a status of 'CLOSED'. Action buttons are now 'SEND EVALUATION' and 'OPEN CASE'. The 'Case' tab is active, displaying:

- INFORMATION:** Missing From: 03/07/2018, Date Of Birth: 19/07/2016.
- ADMINISTRATORS:** Network Manager: Kate Pappa, Case Manager: Maria Papadopoulou.
- CLOSURE ANNOUNCEMENT:** A section containing three paragraphs of placeholder text (Lorem ipsum) describing the closure process.

 The 'Provide information' button is visible at the bottom left of the sidebar area.

Figure 2-108 Organisation Coordinator – Case Management – Closed case

2.8 Organisation Owner

2.8.1 Dashboard

Figure 2-109 Organisation Owner – Dashboard

Figure 2-110 Organisation Owner – Notifications

2.8.2 Organisations

Figure 2-111 Organisation Owner – Organisations list

Figure 2-112 Organisation Owner – My Organisations – Organisation details

Figure 2-113 Organisation Owner – My Organisations – Organisation details

Figure 2-114 Organisation Owner – My Organisations – Organisation members

Figure 2-115 Organisation Owner – My Organisations – Organisation active cases

Figure 2-116 Organisation Owner – My Organisations – Organisation archived cases

2.9 ChildRescue Administrator

2.9.1 Organisations

Figure 2-117 ChildRescue Administrator – Organisations list

Figure 2-118 ChildRescue Administrator – View organisation

The screenshot shows the 'Create Organization' page in the ChildRescue Administrator interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Organizations (highlighted), Cases, Investigation do's and don'ts, and About ChildRescue. At the bottom of the sidebar is a 'Provide information' button. The main content area has a search bar at the top right with the text 'John Doe' and a dropdown arrow. Below the search bar is a breadcrumb trail: 'Home / Create Organization'. The title of the page is 'Create Organization'. The form contains several fields: 'Organization Thumbnail*' with a 'Browse...' button; 'Organization Name*' with a text input field containing 'Name'; 'Organization Type*' with a dropdown menu showing 'Select Type'; 'Organization Description*' with a large text area containing 'Description'; 'Organization E-mail*' with a text input field containing 'E-mail'; and 'Organization Owner E-mail*' with a text input field containing 'E-mail'. At the bottom of the form are two buttons: a grey 'CANCEL' button and an orange 'CREATE ORGANIZATION' button.

Figure 2-119 ChildRescue Administrator – Create new organisation

3 Conclusions

The present document presented the results of the first iteration of “T3.2 - Platform Development and Deployment” and “T3.3 – Mobile App Design and Development” which consists of a low fidelity, functional mock-up version of the platform that will be delivered for early assessment by the end users. The implemented mockups were developed in three iterations making use of the outcomes of “D1.1 - User Requirements”, “D1.3 - ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release I” and the input from the ChildRescue pilots and consortium through organised workshops and bilateral discussions. The mockups will guide the development of the first prototype of the ChildRescue Platform.

Annex I: Updated User stories

The following table provides the updated user stories of D1.1 based on the feedback provided by the pilots during the Second Plenary Meeting, 6-7 November 2018 in Frankfurt.

Table 1 Updated User Stories

#	EPIC	USER STORY from D1.1			UPDATED USER STORIES	
		ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT	GOAL/DESIRE	BENEFIT
			I want...	, so that...	I want...	, so that...
VU.01	Registration	Visitor	to be able to register using minimal details or by using social media accounts	I can be part of the ChildRescue platform.		
VU.02	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view a list of currently active missing children cases	I can actively participate in the investigation.	to be able to view a list of currently active missing children cases near my vicinity, if my geolocation is enabled	I can actively participate in the investigation.
VU.02.1	Platform Browsing	Visitor	N/A	N/A	to have only one active notification per case	I have a clear overview of all cases and my device is not spammed with notifications.
VU.03	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to sort the list of missing children based on their disappearance date	I can see the most recent ones.		
VU.04	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to visit the page of a single case	I can view more details concerning the case.		

VU.05	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view a list of the participating Organisations and their contact details	I can communicate with Organisations by other means, such as telephone or postal services.		
VU.06	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about the platform, terms of service and usage, etc	I can be fully aware of what the platform is about and what requirements it involves.		
VU.07	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about DOs and DON'Ts regarding missing children investigation.	I can assist the investigation in an appropriate and correct - for the child at risk - manner.	to be able to view information about DOs and DON'Ts regarding missing children investigation.	I can assist the investigation in an appropriate for the child at risk manner, abiding by the law and respecting human rights.
VU.08	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to send feedback in the form of text, image or video to the Organisation concerning a missing child by filling-in an appropriate form	I can assist in the investigation mission anonymously.		
VU.08.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	N/A	N/A	to be able to submit a piece of information, even for a case I am not informed about with a notification (e.g. if I meet a child alone on the street)	I can assist also in cases that I am not actively informed about through ChildRescue.

SU.01	Registration	Simple User	to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process	I can have a more complete and reliable personal profile which increases my integrity thus making me a trusted collaborator.		
SU.02	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to edit my personal profile information	I can have a more complete personal profile which increases my integrity and reliability.		
SU.03	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to allow geolocation services	I can be contacted based on my current location.		
SU.04	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to permanently remove my account credentials from the system	I can no longer log-in and not be contacted by other users.	to be able to use my "right to be forgotten" under the GDPR, and permanently remove my account from the system	I can no longer log-in and not be contacted by other users.
SU.05	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to make my profile "private" or hide my details	I can safekeep my anonymity in respect to my peers.		
SU.06	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to apply for volunteer for a selected Organisation	I can offer my services in a more official and permanent way and get more privileges in the platform.	to get informed on the process to become a volunteer for a specific organisation	I can offer my services in a more official and permanent way and get more privileges in the platform.

SU.07	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to view a list of currently missing children, last seen around my current location	I can actively search for them.	to view a list of currently missing children, last seen around my current location	I can have an open eye for them.
SU.08	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to sort the list of missing children based on their disappearance date	I can see the most recent ones.		
SU.09	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to filter out cases based on physical characteristics, such as age, hair colour, clothing	I can focus on the right case, in situations where I have a clear live view of a child.	REMOVED STORY	
SU.10	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to be able to share information about a case on my social media accounts	I further disseminate information about the case to a larger audience.	REMOVED STORY	
SU.11	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to be able to view a list of the participating Organisations and their contact details	I can establish a communication channel with an Organisation directly through the platform.		
SU.11.1	Platform Browsing	Simple User	N/A	N/A	to see statistics (e.g. cases solved per country) in front page if there are no active cases in vicinity, or as menu item if there are	I have a general picture of the work done by the organisations.

SU.12	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to send feedback in the form of text, image or video to the Organisation concerning a missing child without the need to fill-in a long form	I can assist in the investigation mission in a quick and efficient manner.	to send geotagged and timestamped feedback in the form of text, image or video to the Organisation concerning a missing child without the need to fill-in a long form	I can assist in the investigation mission in a quick and efficient manner.
SU.13	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when I have a direct message received	I know a response to my message was provided.	to get notified when I have a direct message received	I know that there is a response to the information I uploaded .
SU.14	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to be able to view messages sent to me and reply	I can continue communication with an Organisation/ Team.		
SU.15	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when there is a missing child case in my vicinity	I can act on it and help the investigation.		
SU.16	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when announcements are made concerning a case in my vicinity	I can be informed with latest news regarding the case.	REMOVED STORY	
SU.16.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	N/A	N/A	to have the option to select and "follow" specific cases	I still receive notifications for them, even when I am outside the notification area.
SU.17	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when a case is closed	I can stop any actions I have taken.	to get notified when a case I follow or had been notified for	I can stop any actions I have started.

					(even once), is closed	
SU.18	Investigation Crowd-sourcing Action	Simple User	to evaluate a piece of information, if requested	I can validate if it is true or false according to my knowledge.		
RT.01	Profile Editing	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.		
RT.02	Investigation Coordination/Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to get rapidly notified when there is a missing child case and my team is required	I can act on it, get the team assembled and help the investigation in the field.	to get rapidly notified when there is a missing child case and my contribution is required	I can act on it and help the investigation in the field.
RT.02.1	Investigation Coordination/Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	N/A	N/A	to be able to decline an invitation to join investigation team and continue as a simple user for this specific case if at all	if i am not able to actively participate as a team member, still be able to help and receive location-based notifications as any simple registered user.
RT.03	Investigation Coordination/Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to have access to a discussion channel with my team-members and case coordinators	I can get communicate with my team in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages.	to have access to a collaboration space with other team-members and case coordinators	I can communicate with my team in a secure and private virtual space.

RT.03.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	N/A	N/A	to be able to turn my geolocation off temporarily, but continue receiving the messages and notifications of the discussion team	I can pause and rest from an active investigation I am taking part in, but still be updated with latest news.
RT.03.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	N/A	N/A	to be able to quit from an investigation case and the related collaboration space	I can disengage from the search operations of this case and the respective team's affairs.
RT.04	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to upload/download files of information in the discussion channel	I can exchange multimedia files, like photos or videos, with team members and my superiors.	REMOVED STORY	
RT.05	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to get guidance and real-time profiling information about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.	to get guidance and real-time announcements about the case from my superiors	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.
RT.05.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	N/A	N/A	to have a list of the tasks I was assigned and be able to mark them when done	I have a clear overview of what I have to do.
RT.06	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Member	to be able to watch my current location, as well as other team members' locations, on an interactive map	I can have a clear overview of the team's current situation and the	REMOVED STORY	

				area each member covers.		
TL.01	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	N/A	N/A	to be able to watch my current location, as well as other team members' locations, on an interactive map	I can have a clear overview of the team's current situation and the area each member covers.
TL.02	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	N/A	N/A	to get guidance and real-time announcements about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.
TL.03	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R/Volunteer Team Leader	N/A	N/A	to have access to a collaboration space with teams and case coordinators with the ability to upload/download files	I can offer the necessary information (e.g. a profile record) to the investigation group or my superiors.
FM.01	Profile Editing	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.		

FM.02	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to fill in extended profiling information about an unaccompanied migrant minor residing in the premises	I can keep track of the minors I am responsible for		
FM.03	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to find a minor that is documented in the system using multiple profiling criteria and fuzzy matching	when a minor comes to my care, I can have access to his history and be able to notify other facilities that the minor isn't missing	to automatically match a new child profile with existing profiles using multiple criteria	I can identify if a newcoming minor has been registered before or belongs to another facility.
FM.04	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to upload documents to the platform concerning the children of my facility	there is a repository of profile records with the corresponding digital files (e.g. id papers, forms, etc).		
FM.04.1	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to save the case info and documents in the ChildRescue platform	I can easily find and make changes to the history of a minor under my responsibility.
FM.05	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit/replace the documents I have uploaded to the platform	there is always the updated version of all pieces of information regarding a profile record.		
FM.06	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to rapidly notify the Organisation when there is a case of a missing child in my facility	they can act on it and follow the appropriate procedures.		

FM.07	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	the system to automatically notify the managers of other facilities where the child has been before or has friends/relatives there	more people get notified that are relevant to the case.		
FM.08	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to have access to a collaboration space with teams and case coordinators with the ability to upload/download files	I can offer the necessary information (e.g. a profile record) to the investigation group or my superiors.	REMOVED STORY	
FM.09	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to ask other facility managers for their input in case they have historical data concerning the same child	I can exchange information with other facilities.		
FM.10	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to get guidance and real-time information about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.		
CM.01	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to fill in the basic information about a new missing child case	I can provide basic details on that case.		
CM.01.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to upload a scanned document of signed consent	I can have documents related to a case gathered and easily retrievable.
CM.01.2	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to save the case info and documents in the	I can easily find and make changes to the history of a minor under my responsibility.

					ChildRescue platform	
CM.01.3	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to have access to all cases	I can handle whichever case I am assigned from the Coordinator and information is not lost between different shifts.
CM.01.4	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to automatically match a new child profile with existing profiles using multiple criteria and intelligent methods	I can check if its a multiple case or if there is an active tracing request
CM.01.5	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to find a case that is documented in the system using multiple profiling criteria	I can see if it is a multiple case, or there are other cases with strong resemblance.
CM.02	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to update the information of a case with more details or specify crucial information (like location last seen, latest info gathered, etc.)	I can offer an updated description of a case.	to update and extend the information of a case with more details or specify crucial information (like location last seen, latest info gathered, etc.)	I can offer an updated description of a case.
CM.02.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to update an open case whenever new	all case data is stored in a well-maintained and continuous manner.

					information occurs	
CM.03	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to upload relevant multimedia files (e.g. pic of child)	I can offer a more informed description of a case.		
CM.04	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add social media accounts of the child	I can enhance the profiling process by using knowledge extraction on social profile preferences, activities, public posts, etc.		
CM.05	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add psychological reviews, witness reports, etc	I can enhance the profiling details of the missing child.		
CM.05.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to perform profiling analytics	I can have insights and predictions on behavioural patterns of the case.
CM.06	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to close and archive a finished case	All people involved get notified and the case is no longer displayed as active.		
CM.07	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to engage in real time discussions with user groups (e.g. volunteers, rescue teams)	I can carry forward relevant information in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages.		

CM.07.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to set up a collaboration space dedicated to the missing child case and a specified general location (ex. Case 128 in Ioannina)	I can invite rescue and volunteer teams close to the area, monitor and manage them.
CM.08	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload/download files of information in the discussion channel	I can exchange multimedia files, like photos or videos, with the case members.		
CM.09	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to communicate with the Network Manager	I can pass location-based information to the investigation procedure on the field.		
CM.10	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to contact and get guidance by the Organisation Coordinator	I can act in a more efficient way regarding the available resources.		
CM.11	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to initiate a crowd-sourcing evidence validation process	I can receive feedback on the validity of a piece of information.		
CM.12	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to configure the settings of the validation process	I can focus the process to a specific centre and range.		
CM.13	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to issue global news and announcements about a case	I can notify all users of important news	REMOVED STORY	

CM.13.1	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	all notifications sent through the platform to the general public to include only information approved by the authorities	the whereabouts of the missing child cannot be inferred and malicious use of the platform is prevented.
CM.13.2	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to configure the dissemination area of the notifications that will be sent to users based on the data analytics results and my expertise	crowdsourcing is more focused and efficient.
CM.14	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to issue directions and information to group of users based on their location	I can notify only users that are actually near a point of interest	REMOVED STORY	
CM.15	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to get real-time feedback from all available human resources (e.g. citizens, anonymous users)	I can gather all possible information		
CM.16	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able through the platform to monitor missing children's social accounts for new public posts	I may extract information on their whereabouts.		
CM.17	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to monitor the overall progress of the investigation	I can understand at which state it is		

CM.18	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to view all information about a case, sent by all participants, in historical order	I can have a more detailed view on the progress of the investigation		
CM.18.1	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	every case in my dashboard to have a notification sign	I can distinguish cases with updates which I haven't seen yet.
CM.18.2	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to easily handle cases of siblings, correlate them and avoid double typing	I work more efficiently but at the same time cover all possible scenarios (children are together or separated).
CM.18.3	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to create a list of missing people cases which will be correlated	I can handle a natural disaster incident efficiently and quickly.
CM.18.4	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to ensure that all evidence from users will remain logged and unchanged	the platform operates based on integrity and trust.
CM.19	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to evaluate the information gathered	I can distribute the important pieces to the relevant teams		
CM.20	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to send my evaluation and current status to the Coordinator	the important information propagates to the top.		
CM.21	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	to semantically tag a case	it can be easier matched to similar past or future cases.

CM.22	Archiving	Organisation Case Manager	N/A	N/A	the case data of a closed case to be deleted from the users' devices within a fixed period of time	the privacy of the child and family is protected after closure.
NM.01	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	To get notified as soon as there is a new case that requires my skills	I can act rapidly to assemble the appropriate teams		
NM.02	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to notify all Search and Rescue Teams or/and Volunteer Teams to log in to the platform	we can setup a collaboration space about the case and the investigation.	to be able to invite available Volunteer/S&R members, to join collaboration space	we can setup a collaboration space about the case and the investigation.
NM.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to notify with free-text message all volunteers of local S&R Teams or/and Volunteer Teams of the new case and receive their availability	I can setup teams for the investigations and give volunteers some basic contact details.
NM.02.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to receive a confirmation of delivery for every invitation I have sent to volunteers	I know if my notification has reached the members.
NM.02.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to manually assign the team leader of every	it is easier to coordinate separate teams.

					volunteer/S&R team from the available members	
NM.02.4	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to contact other organisations' network managers that also use the ChildRescue platform and ask for help in resources	the required human and other resources are assembled for the operations.
NM.02.5	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to notify new members and teams to join the collaboration space according to the investigation progress, especially if a new geographical location is suggested	adequate rescuers and volunteers are participating in each stage and place of the investigation.
NM.03	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to have access or be able to create a discussion channel with the team-members and case coordinators	I can guide my teams in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages	to be able to engage in real time discussions with selected team leaders and case managers	I can guide my teams in a secure and private virtual space.
NM.03.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to be able to post announcements for all team members	I can give one-way instructions to the teams, which will be easily viewable.

					participating in the case to view, similar to a news feed	
NM.03.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to mark important announcements in the timeline with different colour (highlight them somehow)	the volunteers can easily see what I think is important.
NM.03.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	assign tasks to participating team members	they can have a clear view of what they have to do
NM.03.4	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	N/A	N/A	to create chat rooms with selected members from the volunteer/S&R teams for communications	I can instantly exchange information with team leaders.
NM.04	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to communicate with the Case Manager in real-time	I can get the required information for the case.		
NM.05	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to contact and get guidance by the Organisation Coordinator	I can be constantly informed about all cases' status and distribute human resources accordingly and more efficiently		

NM.06	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to view where all field resources (humans, vehicles, dogs) are located in real-time	I can be constantly informed about the status and whereabouts of all field resources		
NM.07	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to monitor the current progress of the investigation location-wise	I can direct teams to search in specific areas		
NM.08	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to view predictions regarding the possible routes of the missing child	I can direct teams to search in specific areas		
NM.09	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to send my evaluation and current status to the Coordinator	the important information propagates to the top.		
OC.01	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Coordinator	To have access to all cases' information and be able to edit, open or close a case	I have total control of all cases.		
OC.02	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to contact all Case and Network Managers	I can coordinate all available resources.		
OC.02.1	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	N/A	N/A	to be able to send the case file and documents to organisations in another country	I can rapidly inform and activate legitimate organisations in case of a cross-border country
OC.03	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to engage in real time discussions with user groups (e.g.	I can get real-time feedback from a group of people.	to be able to engage in real time discussions with user groups	I can carry forward relevant information in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages.

			volunteers, rescue teams)		(e.g. volunteers, rescue teams)	
OC.04	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to issue global news and announcements about any case	I can notify all users of important news.	REMOVED STORY	
OC.05	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to contact each and every user of the platform personally	I can send and get personalised feedback.		
OC.06	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to monitor the overall progress of all the active investigations	I can understand at which state is each case and what assistance is required.		
OC.07	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to monitor the progress of all active investigations location-wise	I can guide the Network Manager accordingly.		
OC.08	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to view all cases current and past and their full details	I have access to all available information.		
OC.09	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to assign Case and Network Managers for each case	each case is covered in the most efficient way.		
OC.09.1	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	N/A	N/A	to have access to the activity history of all case managers	I have a clear overview of the taken actions and be able to allocate cases accordingly.
OC.10	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to file a report regarding the management of each case	there is a complete archive for each investigation, not only regarding the goal, but also about the procedures		

				followed by all participants.		
OC.11	Archiving	Organisation Coordinator	N/A	N/A	to aggregate data from past cases	useful outcomes are provided to be exploited in the future, in a manner always respecting privacy matters.
OC.12	Archiving	Organisation Coordinator	N/A	N/A	statistics to be generated from every case and to be correlated	I gain insights in the performance of the organisation.
OO.01	Organisation Information Filling	Organisation Owner	N/A	N/A	to receive invitation to activate my Organisation's profile in ChildRescue	I take control of the new profile and start managing it.
OO.01.1	Organisation Information Filling	Organisation Owner	to be able to set and edit the basic information about my Organisation	I can provide an informative profile of the Organisation.		
OO.02	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to view a list of all available users belonging to my Organisation and at what position	I can have an overview of our human resources assignments	to be able to view a list of all available users belonging to my Organisation and at what position and location	I can have an overview of our human resources assignments
OO.03	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to send invitations via e-mail to my personnel and associated teams to join the platform	I can invite them to join the platform and gather all my human resources in		

				this collaboration platform.		
00.04	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to setup and assign roles for the Organisation members (Case Manager, Network Manager, Coordinator, Volunteer Team member, Search & Rescue Team member)	I can manage the access privileges of my users to the available information and functionality.		
00.05	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to remove users from my Organisation	I can reorganise our human resources		
00.06	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to delete my Organisation	it is no longer part of the ChildRescue platform		
00.07	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of all active cases and the human resources (e.g. Organisation members, Volunteers, etc) assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the current effort and possible deficiencies		
00.08	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of the duration of all historical cases and the human resources assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the past performance of my staff		
00.09	Organisation Communication	Organisation Owner	to accept and reply to messages directed to my Organisation by simple users or visitors of the platform	I can respond to user requests/complaints towards the Organisation		
00.10	Organisation Communication	Organisation Owner	to be able to communicate with other Organisations	we can cooperate together in a mission or cause		

OO.11	Organisation Policy	Organisation Owner	N/A	N/A	all case data to be anonymised	the privacy of the family and the child are protected and my organisation is aligned to the GDPR requirements.
OO.12	Organisation Policy	Organisation Owner	N/A	N/A	all case data to be encrypted	I ensure my organisation's compliance to the GDPR.
CA.01		ChildRescue Administrator	N/A	N/A	to create the organisation profile and add organisation owner	the organisation can use ChildRescue.